

ENDOGENOUS PRICE CHANGES IN CHINAS MUTTON MARKET: EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

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Abstract

The persistent fluctuations in agricultural prices in countries like China have rekindled interest in the concept of endogenous price instability. Our study examines the causes of Chinese mutton price volatility. We created a theoretical framework to account for endogenous price changes in China's mutton supply chain. Field research and unobserved component model estimations inform our methodology. Our theoretical framework uses vector auto regressions and monthly Chinese sheep and mutton prices to derive hypotheses that may be tested under conventional assumptions. Our actual analysis matches our theoretical framework. Endogenous dynamics in prices are resilient to model specifications and estimating approaches. Descriptive, empirical, and numerical analyses support price instability in China's mutton supply chain being endogenous.

Keywords: Endogenous Price Fluctuation, Agricultural Supply Chain, Mutton Supply

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector holds significant importance in the economies of developing nations, serving as the primary means of food, income, and employment for rural communities. It is imperative for developing nations such as China to maintain the growth of their agricultural sector. Over the course of recent decades, significant fluctuations have transpired in agricultural output. The health of the nation as a whole is highly dependent on how well the agricultural economy works. Above all, it is essential to ensure sustainable food security, employment and livelihoods for almost one-third of the world's population (FAO, 2013).

Variations in agricultural prices have a detrimental effect on the stability and growth of the economy of nations. The negative consequences of agricultural price instability on countries are exacerbated

by factors such as inefficient supply networks, lack of storage space, and restricted access to risk-sharing markets among farmers. As a result, farmers in these nations experience significant price risk and struggle to production planning results in social unrest and food insecurity (Barrett et al., 2010).

China is skilled at producing and eating mutton, according to Ding CZ et al. (2016). One of the most popular type of meat consumed by China's locals is mutton. China's mutton industry has grown quickly since the country's reform and opening up, and its output have significantly increased. For years, China has ranked first in the world for mutton production (Liu Y et al., 2019). The amount of mutton produced nationally in 2019 was 4.8752 million tons. The growth of the China mutton business has been steady, and it has become a cornerstone of animal husbandry because to the countries growing economy and the enhancement of the tourism industry. Nonetheless, the business still faces some issues that limit its ability to compete.

Mutton prices have shown a shifting pattern over the last few years due to the steadily rising demand for the meat. As a result, it is extremely useful to study what factors contribute to the ups and downs of China's mutton market. The extant literature shows that numerous researchers have investigated the topic of mutton price volatility from both theoretical and empirical angles. (Yang et al., 2022). Over time, mutton sheep breeding practices shifted from extensive and limited free-range breeding to intensive and widespread indoor feeding. It produces more mutton than any other country (Ding, 2014). Nonetheless, the mutton market continues to be characterized by limited supply, and China's mutton sheep industry is highly vulnerable to the effects of both natural disasters and market fluctuations. (Li and Jin, 2019).

Feed factors, including as price fluctuations and feeding costs, have an effect on the cost of raising mutton. The key factors influencing mutton pricing in China are supply, feeding expenses, and consumer demand. Using data on global mutton prices, beef prices, feed prices, the consumer price index, and Xinjiang mutton prices (Long and Liu, 2014) built a "vector autoregressive" (VAR) model and examined the effects of different parameters via impulse response analysis and empirical model decomposition (EMD). The results indicated that the shortage of availability and high breeding expenses were the primary variables impacting the price of mutton in China.

Huili and Wenge (2020) found that income level and mutton pricing significantly affect per capita mutton ingesting, while the weight of the carcass and number of sheep have a major influence on China's veal output. The price of mutton is expected to increase in tandem with both supply and demand. Changes in the cost of living, income, and the ratio of urban to rural consumers all play a role in setting the market price for mutton. External conventional elements that affect the volatility of the mutton price include demand and supply, as well as the cost of agriculture and related items, alternatives, and population size (Yang et al., 2022).

According to the research that numerous academics have investigated the topic of mutton price volatility from both within and outside the industry. For the past ten years, has occurred in China's mutton supply chain, where continuous Price swings have deterred investments in the goat meat production and prompted thousands of farmers facing bankruptcy (Khan et al., 2014).

This study employs data from the endogenous literature on agricultural pricing to undertake fieldwork, based on a theoretical model, in order to show that price volatility in the Chinese mutton supply chain is, in fact, endogenous. We provide data from numerical simulations and describe the results of hypothesis testing.

Arango and Moxnes (2012) showed strategies based on external price volatility have not been successful in reducing the volatility of agricultural prices in LDCs (Galtier, 2013). The literature presents various models that have been developed to study the dynamics of commodity prices. As illustrated

by Chaudhry and Miranda (2018), such models include cobweb-type models that integrate speculators and market interlinkages. Additionally, there are nonlinear cobweb models that account for heterogeneous expectations, as proposed by Hommes (2018). Another model that has been used to analyse commodity prices is the competitive storage model, which was introduced by Oglend and Kleppe (2017). “Nonlinear cobweb-type models” with supply shocks (Westerhoff & Dieci, 2010) and reasonable storing models with simple prospects (Mitra & Boussard, 2012) are just two examples of the enhancements that have been used to study the integration of exogenous and endogenous price variations in the literature.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Many developing countries, like China, have agricultural growth and food security as one of their top policy priorities. Nonetheless, there are regional and national variations in the amount of progress gained in emerging nations. When researching the growth of agriculture, China is one of the most fascinating cases to look at. Throughout the previous 25 years, at the national level, agriculture has grown at a roughly four times yearly rate greater than population expansion. Unlike what many past analysts had predicted China's increased reliance on agricultural imports will derive from its fast industrialization despite the economy's stabilization and liberalization, there hasn't been an increase in net food imports. China has been a net exporter of agricultural and food items for over two decades (NSBC, 1981-2002), despite the country's rapid economic development and policy reforms.

China has made remarkable progress in boosting agricultural output at the family level, ensuring food security, and reducing the prevalence of malnutrition over the past two decades. Over 30% of rural Chinese fell into poverty by the late 1970s, but by 1990 that number had dropped to 10% (NSBC, 2002). By 2001, that number had risen to 12%.

The price of meat in China has gone up and down multiple times over the past 20 years. Changing meat prices have an important influence on inflation in China, and this literature aims to explain why. There have been attempts to explain why food price increases correlate with overall price increases in the economy. Many economists and government officials, according to Liang and Long (2014), worry that rising grain prices may lead to inflation. The specific method of expression at play here is that rising food prices are pushing up grain prices, which in turn will push up inflation. Meat is also a staple in the Chinese diet and a staple in the Chinese food market. China's food demand has been steadily increasing for a variety of reasons, including rising incomes and populations. In addition, China's domestic meat supply is insufficient, therefore imports play a significant role in maintaining market stability. As a result, the Chinese market will experience a meat shortage in the case of a catastrophic occurrence, such as the spread of swine flu, among international suppliers. Therefore, it is plausible to assume that the price will go up, and inflation will follow (Han and Wu, 2019).

However, present achievements do not guarantee future agricultural production or food safety. Recent analyses have generally concluded that China's rising food and grain imports will not lead to widespread hunger elsewhere, China still has a significant problem ahead of it to feed its expanding population in the future while also continuously raising rural income (World Bank, 1997). Since rapid industrialization and urbanization will cause competition for resources between the agricultural and non-agricultural sectors, China's future ability to feed itself will depend on agricultural productivity growth and the availability of resources (such as water and land) for agricultural production..

2.1 Agriculture in China

Topographic and climatic constraints limit China's total cultivable land area to only about 10%. After years of water-saving efforts, little more than half of the land is now irrigated, with the other half split between paddy fields and irrigated areas. The soil quality varies from region to region, and many regions are in danger due to drought, flooding, and erosion. Only 10% of China's total land area is cultivable due to factors such as geography and climate. The majority of water conservation efforts have taken place in non-irrigated areas, with the remainder approximately equally divided between irrigated and paddy fields. However, environmental issues like as erosion, drought, and floods pose significant threats to agricultural production in many locations.

Tibet, Xinjiang, and Qinghai are all part of Western China, and they are not particularly important for farming outside of a few oasis farming and cow ranching districts. Rice is most essential crop in China, and the southern provinces are where it's grown and harvested twice a year. In the northern part of the country, wheat is king, but in the central part of the country, rice and wheat are neck-and-neck for prominence. Kaoliang and Millet (a type of grain sorghum) are primarily grown in the Northeast, certain central provinces, and certain northern regions. The North and the Midwest are responsible for the majority of the nation's corn (maize) crop, whereas the North and the Northeast are responsible for the vast majority of the soybean crop. Tea is cultivated predominantly in the southeast, namely in the region's hilly terrain. Central provinces grow a lot of cotton, while the southeast and the north grow far less. Tobacco is grown in the South and in some parts of the Midwest. Potatoes, sugar beets, and oilseeds are three other major crops.

Animal husbandry is the agriculture sector's second most important contributor. China is the world spearhead chickens and in the production of pigs, and eggs, and it also has large herds of sheep and cattle. Since the mid-1970s, there has been a greater focus on increasing livestock productivity.

Major agricultural products

China's agricultural land, which makes up around 10% of the world's total agricultural land, is responsible for feeding about 20% of the world's population. Only 1.2% (116,580 sq km) of this potentially productive land is actually farmed on a permanent basis, with only 525,800 sq km receiving irrigation (Gouel, 2012). Each of the world's roughly 200 million households has only 0.65 hectares (1.6 acres) of land.

Livestock

The most common forms of livestock in China are sheep, goats, and chickens. Nomadic herders in rural western China keep sheep, goats, and camels. In Tibet, yaks are raised for their wool, meat, and hides as well as for their dung, which is used to build houses. Cattle, donkeys, mules, buffalo and horses are also raised in China, and the government has recently encouraged the consumption of dairy products, despite the fact that about 92.3% of the adult population suffers from lactose intolerance.

2.2 Inefficiencies in the agricultural market

Despite significant gains in productivity, the Chinese agriculture sector continues to struggle with a variety of challenges. Farmers in many provinces, including Zhejiang, Anhui, Shandong, Xinjiang and Liaoning sometimes have trouble selling their agricultural products to consumers due to a lack of understanding about current situations.

These information and transportation problems underscore the inefficiencies in the market mechanisms between producers and end consumers, making it difficult for producers to reap the benefits of the rapid expansion of the rest of the Chinese economy. To support the Chinese economy

as a whole, farmers would benefit from investing in agricultural inputs (equipment, seeds, fertiliser, etc.), but their poor profit margin prevents them from doing so. This causes an increase in the population of already overcrowded urban areas. In a speech given in September of 2020, Xi Jinping, general secretary of the Chinese Communist Party, ordered Chinese scientists to conduct research on seed culture. He brought up the country's dependence on imported seed and encouraged its scientists to help discover a solution.

2.3 Extreme Events

The confrontation between Russia and Ukraine, the Covid-19 epidemic, and infectious diseases are just a few of the dramatic events. The possible vulnerabilities in the food supply chain have come to light as a result of these extreme instances (Bellemare et al., 2012).

A widespread understanding that, going forward, macro dynamics are expected to make countries more vulnerable to such shocks increases the urgency of researching food supply resilience to such catastrophes (Marani et al., 2012). For instance, the majorities of infectious diseases that are currently on the rise begin in wild animals and spread through interactions with humans, domestic animals, and other species in a constantly changing environment. Increasing human-wildlife contact therefore increases the risk of pandemics.

The cattle industry, especially the global production of mutton, was severely impacted by the COVID-19 epidemic, which had far-reaching consequences for many other areas of society as well. Several countries took precautions, including limiting travel, increasing border inspections, and locking down their borders. Supply networks and output suffered as a result of these efforts. Compromises in mutton production and processing can be traced back to a number of factors, including a lack of available production inputs like animal feed, transportation restrictions (such as seasonal border crossing restrictions), skilled labour, and access to markets. Because of these issues, meat production and processing plant capacities fell, leading to lower sales and a slowdown in the market.

Figure 1: Showing Effect of Covid-19 on Mutton Source Chain and Production

The analysis of the internal and external factors impacting the price of mutton has advanced greatly in recent research. While previous research has addressed some of the factors that influence mutton prices, the internal and external factors that do so have not been studied to the same extent. There isn't nearly enough focus on the underlying mechanics. This article employed a data decomposition strategy combined with a correlation analysis to look at the external and internal elements that have an influence on the price of mutton in China, as well as the process by which these factors fluctuate.

3.0 METHODS AND DATA SOURCES

3.1 Analytical model

Figure 2: Mutton price fluctuations: a multi-scale analytical framework

The findings of the present study are illustrated in Figure 2, which showcases the utilization of data disintegration and association investigation to identify the principal factors that determine the fluctuations in mutton prices. The existing framework can be delineated into three discrete stages, as illustrated below:

1. **Decomposition method:** Using the signal decomposition method, the original data was broken down into simpler modes or constituents in order to better understand the complex underlying time series. This stage involved the application of ensemble empirical mode decomposition (EEMD).
2. **Granger Causality analysis:** The fundamental goal of the connection study was to investigate the correlates of each factor. The “Granger causality test” was utilized to examine the correlation among the variables in the cost of mutton series and their causes.
3. **Analysis of key factors:** The primary drivers of mutton price volatility were identified using Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

3.2 “Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition Model”

Wu and Huang devised the “Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition (EEMD)” method to address the inadequacies of the “Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD)” strategy. Nonlinear and nonstationary time series analysis makes use of EMD and EEMD methods. In the EEMD technique, white noise is used as a sort of regularization that helps deal with the problem of modal aliasing. In order to create novel series data that approximates the real-time data more precisely, the EEMD

approach blends the original series data with noise. In addition, it provides missing scales to aid in the identification of the real signal in the noise:

The EEMD process involves the following steps:

- Initially, the ensemble size and noise data are determined.
- Then, the initial data is transformed into $x_i(t)=x(t)+\epsilon_i(t)$ by introducing white noise.
- The data containing white noise is then decomposed using the EMD decomposition method into a number of intrinsic mode function (IMF) components.
- This is done multiple times using various white noise.
- After K iterations, we get an average for each part of the IMF.
- The final step is to reconstruct the unique time sequence using the residuals and IMF i.e.

$$x(t) = \sum_{j=1}^K c_j(t) + r_K(t) \quad (1)$$

3.3 Granger Causality Test

This testing is applied to the factors and components of the mutton price decomposition to determine whether or not they are correlated. Conventionally, the formula is used to define Granger causality between two stationary time series:

$$P_r(x_t | I_{t-1} - Y_{t-n}^n) \quad (t = 1, 2, \dots, T) \quad (2)$$

“The conditional probability distribution” of x_t , denoted as $P_r(x_t | I_{t-1})$, is based on the bivariate evidence data” $I_{t-1} = \{X_{t-m}^m, Y_{t-n}^n\}$. $X_{t-m}^m = \{x_{t-m}, \dots, x_{t-1}\}$ and $Y_{t-n}^n = \{y_{t-n}, \dots, y_{t-1}\}$ represent an m-length lag vector of x_t and an n-length lag vector of y_t , respectively. In the event that Equation (2) is rejected through statistical analysis, it can be demonstrated that the series y_t possesses the capability to forecast the series x_t . It can be inferred that there happens a fundamental connection among the variables y_t and x_t , specifically that y_t Granger causes x_t in a strict sense.

3.4 Principal components analysis (PCA)

It is often known as the Karhunen-Loeve (K-L) approach, is a statistical technique for reducing a large amount of data down to a smaller number of meaningful variables. This cause a decrease in the dimensions because the primary data has been mapped onto a much smaller collection. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) has the potential to explain unexpected results by revealing hidden connections between variables.

3.5 Empirical Hypothesis- (Endogenous dynamics in mutton Prices)

The empirical hypothesis posits that endogenous dynamics are responsible for the fluctuations observed in mutton prices in the Chinese market, indicating that these dynamics are driven by internal market forces rather than being exclusively influenced by external factors. Presented below is a comprehensive elucidation of the empirical hypothesis.

The empirical hypothesis suggests that the fluctuations in mutton prices in the Chinese market cannot be attributed entirely to exogenous factors such as variations in input expenses, market demand, or governmental regulations. The statement posits that there exist intrinsic and autonomous mechanisms within the mutton industry that are responsible for the variability of prices. The aforementioned endogenous factors that are specific to the mutton supply chain, such as production decisions, supply and demand interactions, and market expectations, can give rise to internal dynamics (Gouel, 2012). In order to evaluate the hypothesis, researchers would frequently examine

previous pricing data and explore the correlations between lamb prices and pertinent factors. The researchers would utilise statistical methodologies and econometric models to ascertain and quantify the influence of endogenous variables on the fluctuations of prices.

The cobweb model is a dynamic economic model that portrays the interplay between supply and demand in a market across successive periods. The cobweb model can be applied to the mutton supply chain to comprehend the emergence of price fluctuations due to the temporal discrepancies between production and consumption determinations.

The point of intersection between the supply and demand curves establishes the initial equilibrium in the mutton market. The supply of mutton can be influenced by a range of factors, including fluctuations in input costs, variations in weather patterns, and occurrences of disease outbreaks.

In the event of a rise in supply shocks, such as improved weather conditions or increased productivity, the supply curve experiences an outward shift, resulting in a surplus within the market. Consequently, a decrease in prices occurs as a consequence of an oversupply in comparison to the demand. This phenomenon induces producers to curtail their production in the subsequent period, anticipating a decline in prices.

On the other hand, when negative supply shocks occur, such as adverse weather conditions or disease outbreaks, the supply curve shifts inward, leading to a shortage in the market. The phenomenon of scarcity results in an increase in prices due to a situation where demand surpasses the available supply. As a reaction to elevated prices, producers augment their production during the subsequent period, in anticipation of enhanced profitability.

The cyclical behaviour observed in the cobweb model can be attributed to the temporal delays inherent in production and adjustment decisions. In each period, prices exceed the equilibrium, resulting in temporal price volatility. The aforementioned variations transpire intrinsically within the market, propelled by the interdependence of supply and demand dynamics.

The cobweb model can be utilised in the research paper to demonstrate the effects of supply shocks, such as natural disasters or disease outbreaks, on price fluctuations within the mutton supply chain. Through the integration of these variables, the manuscript can evaluate the degree of concurrence between the cobweb model and the observed data, as well as measure the duration and intensity of price instability stemming from internal factors.

Additionally, the cobweb model can be utilised to investigate the efficacy of governmental interventions in mitigating price fluctuations during exceptional circumstances. The implementation of price controls or subsidies can mitigate price volatility by exerting an impact on the actions of both producers and consumers, as an illustration. The effectiveness of policy interventions in mitigating price volatility and promoting market stability can be evaluated by incorporating them into the cobweb model, as demonstrated in this paper.

In general, the cobweb model functions as a valuable conceptual framework for depicting and examining the internally generated price oscillations that are evident in the mutton supply chain within China. This framework takes into account the effects of supply disruptions and governmental interventions. The aforementioned statement presents a dynamic portrayal of market dynamics and furnishes valuable insights into the factors that contribute to price volatility. Additionally, it proposes potential strategies for stabilising prices.

As an illustration, one could employ time series analysis techniques, such as autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) or vector autoregression (VAR), to construct a model that captures the fluctuations in the price of mutton over time. The utilisation of these models would enable the

researchers to effectively capture the delayed impacts of mutton prices on their own values, as well as the interconnections between mutton prices and other pertinent variables.

The hypothesis will be evaluated through the estimation of model parameters and the implementation of hypothesis tests to evaluate the statistical significance of the endogenous factors. In the event that the empirical analysis yields statistically significant associations between mutton prices and the endogenous variables, it would lend support to the empirical hypothesis positing endogenous dynamics in mutton prices.

The primary objective of this study is to verify the hypothesis that endogenous factors are the driving force behind the price fluctuations in the Chinese mutton market. This will be achieved by conducting an analysis of the market dynamics and examining the empirical evidence. Comprehending this concept is of utmost importance for policymakers, market participants, and stakeholders in order to devise efficacious approaches for handling and alleviating price fluctuations in the mutton supply chain. To test this hypothesis, we apply our theoretical model to the study of the mutton industry in China, looking specifically for evidence of endogenous pricing dynamics.

$$\frac{\partial \pi_{i,t+6}}{\partial q_{i,t+6}^B} : p_{t+6}^{-B} \frac{p_t^C}{k_t^B} - \frac{1}{k_t^B} C_i^{B'} \left(\frac{q_{i,t+6}^B}{k_t^B} \right) = 0 \tag{3}$$

Our empirical hypothesis is based on a linear simplification of a nonlinear dynamical system. Topologically, the linearization at equilibrium is the same as the behaviour of a nonlinear dynamical system towards its steady state, as proven by the Hartman Grobman Theorem. In most cases, the dynamics of nonlinear systems far from the steady state can be understood qualitatively using linear approximation methodologies (De la Fuente, 2000).

Table 1: Showing The Origin Data of the mutton index system

Third- class indicator	Inner Mongolia	Xinjiang	Shandong	Hebei	Sichuan	Henan	Gansu	Anhui	Hunan
No. of elevated sheep (10000)	6112	4318	1754	1228	1599	1682	1840	505	662
Mutton production (10000 ton)	104	58	36	30	27	26	23	17	15
Animal farming technical institutions (individual)	1202	1239	1664	1665	4271	1590	1509	1293	2120
Animal farming technician (person)	12306	14490	11186	10641	21471	13418	10702	5549	15404
Total population	2529	2445	10006	7520	8302	9559	2626	6255	6860
Ingesting level of residents	23909	16736	28535	15893	17920	17842	14203	17141	19418
Number of traveler (10000)	11646	10726	78000	57000	57000	66511	23905	63100	67323

Tourism income (100 million yuan)	3440	1822	9200	6141	8923	6751	1540	6197	7173
Sheep stud farm (separate)	439	104	42	51	108	48	181	83	32
Large scale sheep farm	3484	2639	10144	7581	4420	10038	2019	6313	6255
Corporate initiative of catering trade (individual)	326	97	1767	429	1474	1235	362	1213	930
No. of workers in catering originalities (person)	26404	9577	121848	32554	96640	67165	22204	76554	60737
Output value of animal husbandry (10000 yuan)	1201	749	2501	1739	2200	2369	309	1322	1506
Mutton brands favored by customers (separate)	52	8	12	0	0	1	2	0	0
Huge scale sheep farm with more than 500 annual column amount (household)	10741	4983	2325	3133	795	1518	1594	1498	374
Fixed assets investment in farming, forestry, animal agriculture and fishery	1153	639	1610	1873	1492	2676	407	896	1579

4.0 EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

Here, we use China's monthly mutton pricing data as a test case to examine the accuracy of the planned "multi-scale analytical method", which is predicated on univariate multi-scale putrefaction.

To evaluate predictions from our theoretical model, we employ auto regression methods on weekly data on farm-gate ("inflation-adjusted") prices of mutton in China between January 2011 and December 2021. Time sequence data often contains unit roots. As a result, we look at the mutton market's unit root characteristics before settling on an econometric model. Our unit root study shows that mutton prices have unit roots, suggesting that level-based regression models are misleading. Unit root tests prove that first alterations of values are fixed since they allow for accurate OLS estimation of a regression model based on first alterations of values. There are three more things to keep in mind when analyzing the dynamics of mutton pricing in initial differences as part of our inquiry. When

applied to time series variables, first-differencing dampens the long-term dynamics while amplifying the high-frequency components (Lütkepohl & Krätzig, 2004). Working with first-differenced data allows us to zero in on forecasting the immediate trends of observable prices, which is important for testing the assumptions of our theoretical model. As a second point, it is good knowledge that first-differencing can reduce nonlinear dependency in time-series data. Our experimental approach is based on linear assumptions of an assumed nonlinear data-generating process. Finally, the corresponding operation to differentiation is differentiating. When our econometric model is stated in first variances of prices, this gives estimates that are reliable with the incomplete products given by our conjectural exemplary an intuitive interpretation.

4.1 Specification and estimation of Research model

The empirical evidence primarily employs monthly data pertaining to the price of mutton in China, as depicted in Figure 3. The primary rationale for opting for the china is twofold. On the one hand, the mutton sheep business is one of the pillar sectors of local economic development in China, and Xinjiang is one of the five major pastoral areas in China. However, the Chinese government compiles extensive information on mutton sheep pricing and related data because the industry is so vital to the country's economy.

Figure 3: The factors that affect the price of mutton in China

Internal elements include upbringing cost issues and nourishing price considerations; outside aspects include conventional factors and non-traditional factors; and so on. Feeding costs include things like soybean meal price, maize price, and wheat bran price, whereas material and service costs and labour costs are considered when calculating breeding costs. Traditional considerations include the regional economy, the cost of replacements, and the value of agriculture and other products. Prices for corn flour, oil, cotton special flour, japonica rapeseed seed oil, rice, eggs and soybean combined oil are all included in this category of agricultural and related products. Meats including pork, poultry, and fish are included in the cost of alternatives to red meat. The CPI and other public policy revenues are measures of regional economic health. The international price of energy, the international price of livestock products, and the currency rate are all examples of non-traditional factors. The rate takes into account the value of both the US dollar and the Euro. WTI crude oil spot price is a component of

the global energy cost. Mutton and beef prices around the world are included in the international price of animal products. This section employs the 12 internal and external factors mentioned earlier to examine the variability of mutton value, as presented in Table 2. These factors include WTI crude oil spot price, local public revenue, global beef price, global mutton price, filament seed oil price, egg price, chicken price, beef price, , pork price, fish price, labour cost and material and facility prices. This study utilizes monthly data collected between 2010 and 2018, with a training set/test set ratio of 8:2. The research team used a number of resources to gather and organize their data, including the “Wind a database (<http://www.wind.com.cn>)”, “the China Animal Husbandry 8 The statistical Yearbook (2010-2018)”, the country's gathering of cost-benefit data of agricultural commodities from 2010-2018, and “the China Animal Husbandry Information Network”.

Table 2: “Descriptive statistics of mutton price and its 12 influencing factors”

Influencing Factors	Mean	Max	Min	Range	Skew	St. Dev	Kurtosis
Mutton price	51.03	65.00	35.00	28.10	0.17	7.51	-1.17
Local public revenue	95.35	255.34	24.15	218.81	0.82	42.14	0.91
WTI crude oil spot price	81.67	125.45	32.39	91.62	-0.07	25.39	-1.14
World mutton price	6.71	7.00	4.51	2.66	-0.25	0.57	-0.92
World beef price	4.14	5.18	3.01	3.16	1.12	0.62	3.48
Cotton seed oil price	7.80	10.00	5.01	4.50	0.24	1.91	-0.78
Beef price	52.01	64.00	32.10	31.80	-0.54	11.23	-1.43
Chicken price	18.03	23.00	11.00	11.00	-0.32	4.35	0.78
Egg price	8.93	12.00	5.82	6.16	0.35	2.04	-0.64
Fish price	13.00	16.07	10.01	6.01	0.21	3.23	-0.89
Pork price	26.02	32.50	17.00	15.01	-0.76	5.01	-0.13
Material and service cost	955.56	1154.02	543.72	612.08	-1.16	194.55	0.92
Labor Cost	178.18	265.83	123.54	142.34	1.02	46.6	0.28

4.2 Experimental Analysis

The Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) is a data decomposition algorithm that is adaptive in nature and is based on white noise. The outcome of its decomposition is contingent upon the intrinsic attributes of the given data. The various components of decomposition encompass distinct factor information. Consequently, this section primarily employs correlation analysis to examine the relationship between the components that have been decomposed by EEMD and a range of influencing factors. Using EEMD, one can easily see how the mutton value sequence is decomposed into six constituents, labelled IMF1 through IMF6. Six decayed price mechanisms and 12 factors were used to conduct a Granger connection test to determine the relationship among the two sets of variable.

Table 3: Granger causality test analyses of associated variables with IMF1

Influencing Factors	F value	P Value
Local public income	0.765	0.582
WTI crude oil spot price	0.800	0.550
World mutton price	2.461	0.040
Cotton seed oil price	0.714	0.619
World beef price	1.851	0.085
Beef price	0.561	0.922
Chicken value	0.842	0.443
Egg price	0.936	0.547
Fish price	0.591	0.855
Pork price	0.810	0.561
Material and service costs	0.620	0.762
Labor cost	0.752	0.502

Table 4: Granger causality test analyses of associated variables with IMF2

Influencing Factors	F value	P Value
Cotton seed oil price	1.992	0.092
World mutton price	0.845	0.469
World beef price	1.274	0.277
WTI crude oil spot price	1.123	0.367
Pork price	1.265	0.331
Chicken price	0.280	0.941
Beef price	0.871	0.596
Material and service costs	0.425	0.862
Labor cost	1.366	0.234
Fish price	3.765	0.003
Egg price	1.810	0.089
Local public revenue	2.022	0.074

Table 5: Granger causality test analyses of associated variables with IMF3

Influencing Factors	F value	P Value
Local public income	1.012	0.417
WTI crude oil spot value	0.648	0.587
World mutton price	1.560	0.181
World beef price	0.840	0.525
Cotton seed oil value	2.044	0.080
Beef price	2.482	0.036
Chicken price	0.357	0.158
Egg price	1.637	0.158
Fish price	0.959	0.449
Pork price	0.838	0.628
Material and facility costs	1.221	0.303
Labor cost	3.266	0.014

Table 6: Granger causality test analyses of associated variables with IMF4

Influencing Factor	F Value	p Value
World beef value	37.382	0.000
WTI crude oil spot price	13.774	0.000
Material and service costs	37.943	0.000
World mutton price	0.364	0.547

Table 7: Granger causality test analyses of associated variables with IMF5

Influencing Factors	F value	p Value
Local public income	3.509	0.006
Beef price	2.754	0.023
Cotton seed oil price	2.931	0.017
World mutton price	0.557	0.732
World beef price	0.423	0.832
WTI crude oil spot price	1.215	0.308
Pork price	0.803	0.551
Fish price	3.911	0.003
Egg price	1.839	0.113
Labor cost	11.549	0.000
Chicken price	0.913	0.477
Material and facility costs	0.593	0.706

Table 8: Granger causality test analyses of associated variables with IMF6

Swaying Factor	F Value	p Value
Local public revenue	1.479	0.227
Cotton seed oil price	1.833	0.179
World mutton price	2.367	0.127
World beef price	20.734	0.000
WTI crude oil spot price	23.850	0.000
Fish price	0.109	0.744
Beef price	1.729	0.192
Pork price	114.753	0.000
Egg price	0.226	0.636
Chicken price	0.246	0.621
Labor cost	19.399	0.000
Material and service costs	25.287	0.000

For each factor, the issues with a p-value below 0.1 are the most important drivers. Therefore, the global beef and mutton prices are the association factors of IMF1, while the native public financial income, the price of cotton seed oil, the price of eggs, and the price of fish in China are the association issues of IMF2, and the price of cotton seed lubricant, the price of beef, and the cost of labour are the correlation factors of IMF3. IMF1, IMF5, and IMF6 are all affected by the global price of beef; IMF2, IMF3, IMF4, and IMF5 are all affected by the price of cotton seed oil; IMF3, IMF4, and IMF5 are all affected by the price of beef; and IMF3, IMF4, and IMF6 are all affected by the cost of labor. As a result, the cost of inputs like beef, cottonseed oil, and labor have a significant impact on how much Chinese consumers pay for mutton.

Principal components analysis (PCA) employs eigen decomposition, the research team used a number of resources to gather and organize their data, including the database known as wind ("<http://www.wind.com.cn>"), the "China Animal Husbandry 8", "The statistical Yearbook (2010-2018)", the country's gathering of cost-benefit data of agricultural commodities from 2010-2018, and "the China Animal Husbandry Information Network". The "positive semi-definite matrix", and the extraordinary value breakdown of the matrix to address multivariate and multidimensional factor analysis. Consequently, following the application of the "Granger causality test" to examine the correlation factors among the individual components, the PCA technique is employed to discern the principal pouring issues of each constituent.

Table 9: PCA analysis of IMF1 data

Related Factors	Variance Contribution Rate
World mutton price	0.4265
World beef price	0.4264

Table 10: PCA analysis of IMF2 data

Related Factors	Variance Contribution Rate
Fish price	0.2774
Egg price	0.3130
Cotton seed oil price	0.3404
Local public revenue	0.3377

Table 11: PCA analysis of IMF3 data

Related Factors	Variance Contribution Rate
Labor cost	0.4834
Beef price	0.5565
Cotton seed oil price	0.4660

Table 12: PCA analysis of IMF4 data

Related Factors	Variance Contribution Rate
Cotton seed oil price	0.4228
Local public revenue	0.3267
Fish price	0.3846
Labor cost	0.3506
Beef price	0.601

Table 13: PCA analysis of IMF5 data

Related Factors	Variance Contribution Rate
Material and service costs	0.4714
World beef price	0.3407
Chicken price	0.3403
Beef price	0.4285
Cotton seed oil price	0.4568
WTI crude oil spot price	0.4673
Pork price	0.2023
Labor cost	0.3433

Table 14: PCA analysis of IMF6 data

Related Factors	Variance Contribution Rate
World beef price	0.3929
WTI crude oil spot price	0.3941
Material and service costs	0.4210
Labor cost	0.4778
Pork price	0.3489

The IMF1 is significantly influenced by the global mutton price, as indicated by its high adjustment influence rate of 0.4265. The price of fish is the most important factor in determining IMF2, with a 0.2774 variance contribution rate. The price of beef is the single most significant influence in determining IMF3, explaining 0.5565 of the total variance. The price of beef is the key factor in determining IMF4, as indicated by its 0.601 variance contribution rate. The cost of goods and services is the biggest element in IMF5, with a 0.4714 variance contribution rate. IMF6 is most affected by labor costs, which account for 0.4778 of the total variance. Thus, the key factors that affect the price of mutton are the value of alternative goods, the cost of rearing mutton sheep, and the worldwide market value of commodities obtained from animals.

The “quasi-VAR” is utilized as a tool for statistical analysis to examine the experiential implications of our theoretic framework using real-world data. Autoregressive functions embody the equilibrium conditions generated from the theoretical model. Our theoretical approach incorporates sufficient structure into the auto regressions to avoid common drawbacks associated with vector auto regression analysis, such as model overfitting and lack of economic interpretation, thereby ensuring that the accompanying quasi-VAR is not affected by these issues. “OLS “estimates of “VARs” are reliable under normal expectations. We employed OLS to consecutively estimate the price equations

for grill and chicken meat. The HAC estimator, developed by Newey and West, is utilized to tackle auto correlated residuals in time series regressions.

4.3 Model parameterization

Our theoretical model is parameterized using data from literature and fieldwork on mutton network supply chains. Mutton supply chain models commonly utilize combined industry reports, construction statistic and farmer analyses to parameterize manufacture machineries (Luckstead & Devadoss, 2021). This study utilises various sources of data, including farmer interviews, PPA industry reports, farm level production data, government economic surveys and existing sheep science literature (Padilla et al., 2021) to estimate the fixed-proportion production technology of sheep farmers in China. The cost function exponents are tuned to reflect control sheds' higher operating costs in large-scale market compared to open sheds' lower operating costs in small-scale market. China's demand for food-based supplies exhibits inelasticity with respect to price, as per interviews conducted with customers and retailers. Due to the lack of precise evaluation of mutton demand in China, a linear function is employed to depict the retailers' mutton demand based on conventional wisdom. The cost and demand function parameters are calibrated to minimize the difference between observed and simulated prices' first moments, resulting in non-zero cyclical price variations. Due to limitations in available data, certain parameters in our theoretical model have been parameterized based on intuitive reasoning. Our model's parameterization is realistic and closely linked to the Chinese mutton supply chain, enhancing the authenticity of our numerical analysis.

5.0 CONCLUSION

In this study, we investigate the root reasons of price instability in China's mutton supply chain in an effort to empirically test the idea of endogenous price variations. To pinpoint the reasons of the observed price variations, descriptive data from fieldwork on the mutton sector in China is used. We analyze the data to identify the price-adjusting mechanisms in mutton markets and propose a simplified cobweb model to represent China's mutton supply chain. Our theoretical model generates testable hypotheses that can be analyzed through auto-regression techniques. We employ the monthly prices of mutton in China to test our theoretical model, utilizing an econometric model that accounts for the data's characteristics. Results using vector auto regressions support our model's predictions and show that observed prices exhibit endogenous dynamics.

The result shows that rapidly transformation nature of extreme events such as covid-19 virus caused a lot of issues in the mutton meat industry. Because to restrictions on animal exports, the whole mutton food supply chain was badly impacted, logistics and closing of murder house. Farmers and marketers are also unable to sale their live animals since there were no acceptable market. The closure of slaughter houses, processing plants and panic buying caused price volatility and consumer access to mutton meat and other related products were hampered.

This study presents a multi-scale examination of the fluctuation patterns of mutton prices in China. This study examines the connection among diverse apparatuses and multiple swaying aspects. This study employs a methodology of data breakdown and association examination to examine the price instability of mutton sheep, accounting for various influencing factors.

Three primary conclusions can be inferred:

- Future mutton price forecasts should incorporate significant variables such as global beef and cottonseed oil prices, beef prices, and labour costs, as these factors exert a substantial influence on mutton prices.
- The primary determinants that impact the variability of mutton prices encompass the global pricing of animal-derived commodities, the cost of alternative products, and the expenses associated with raising mutton sheep.
- The study suggests that the substitution effect between global mutton and beef prices has a positive influence on the pricing of mutton in China. Fish prices have a negative influence on the prices of mutton in the area, as they are considered substitutes. The services, costs of materials and labor did not have an important influence on the pricing of mutton in China.

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